

BELIEVING IN GOD'S FATE FOR HUMANBEING**To'uchiboyeva Go'zal Bobomurod kizi****International Islamic Academy of Uzbekistan****Second-year Master's student in Islamic Studies**

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается вопрос о том, что такое "qadar" и "qazo", и о том, как не признавать милость Аллаха и не проявлять благодарность за Его милость, о том, как проявлять веру в предопределение, благодарить Аллаха за всё, что Он дарит, и избегать поступков, которые не соответствуют шариату, не называя их "моим предопределением".

Ключевые слова: Qadar (предопределение), qazo (поступки), совершенные по предопределению), фахш (непристойный), спиртосодержащий напиток, феминизм, расизм, пластическая хирургия.

To the extent**The limits of Allah****Believing in the predestination from Allah**

If we examine the reasons why many people deviate from faith in our time, we will see that the cause often lies in the lack of understanding of destiny, unfavorable circumstances, their ignorance or distancing from religion, as well as cruelty and anger, the lack of belief in predestination.

If people knew that Allah creates everything in this world, that all things are created first before Him, that they are written by Allah, and that they are part of His creation, that they are His beings, humble and devoted to His will, their hearts would be calm and peaceful. However, sometimes a person seeks to change the world and begins to struggle against predestination. He rebels against Allah or against people and says before Allah, "O Allah, why have You done this to me?" Because of this, many people nowadays face difficulties.

Example: He is aware of the harm of alcoholic beverages, but he considers them permissible, finds positive aspects in moderate consumption, and uses them. Thus, he does not acknowledge Allah's disapproval of them.

Regarding feminism, in reality, it is created by a woman, but she does not want to be a woman; she wants to be like a man, or vice versa, she does not want to be a man and wants to be

a woman. This dilemma is also related to predestination.

Racism, in this context, also implies prejudice, questioning why Allah created someone with black skin, why He bestowed upon them blessings that were not given to me. If you knew about predestination, you would understand why Allah granted them such blessings and why you were given the blessings you have. Additionally, it should be noted that the relationships between a man and a woman, their marriage, the absence of marriage, or even why a boy is not born to a girl, and vice versa, are also preordained by Allah.

The lack of faith in Qadar and the excessive amount of our problems are linked to our insufficient belief in Qadar, even in politics, such as wars, violence, and killings; everything boils down to Qadar.

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It should also be noted that the relationships between a man and a woman, marriage, the absence of marriage, or even why a boy is not born to a girl, and vice versa, are also preordained by Allah. The lack of faith in Qadar and the excess of our problems are linked to the lack of our faith in Qadar, even in politics, such as wars, violence, and killings; everything comes down to Qadar.

Therefore, according to the opinion of Ahl as-Sunnah wal Jama'ah, being content with Qadar is something else. Regarding committing Qazo (acts predestined by Allah), they express a completely different point of view. "You know that Allah wrote this for you, you believe, you accept it, but the law prohibits you from doing it," they say.

For example, a person who steals something, then robs, and then says, "Allah wrote this for me, what should I do?"

This person does not say, "I stole what concerns me, and now I need to take action." Mushriks (those who worship multiple gods) also, if Allah has decreed kufr (disbelief) for us, what can they do about it, and present it as an argument. Therefore, the question of establishing faith in Qadar is one of the most challenging tasks, and a person needs to delve into it.

The student asked: Is it possible that in our time, 99% of people do not have faith in predestination?

The teacher continued: Because the one who teaches this does not exist. This is a question of the spiritual realm. In reality, the teaching of faith in predestination is imparted by

the Sufis.

Be with Allah.

Be content with the predestination of Allah.

The predestination of Allah only leads to goodness.

Be content with what Allah has bestowed upon you in fate.

Submit to the will of Allah.

Be a servant of Allah.

Therefore, a person acquainted with Tasawwuf (Sufism) sees how a person satisfied with the predestination of Allah enjoys his well-being and happiness. Even if a woman is not considered beautiful in the eyes of others, her heart is very beautiful. In reality, she is beautiful, and even if Satan casts doubts upon her, she considers herself beautiful and will be confident in it. This is the most beautiful aspect, and despite the advancements in surgical operations and changing appearances, there is no happiness.

If you are dissatisfied with your fate, whatever you have will always be displeasing to you. If you are content with your fate, even small things will be a source of joy for you, and you will see more positivity in your surroundings. Being not wealthy, you can enjoy your blessings, and being wealthy, you may experience many dissatisfactions. If you are modest, even with little wealth, you will be happy. Money can buy medicines but not health. You can buy a ticket but not luck. Imagine being poor, but every evening you go to prayer at the mosque, and you are happy because your soul is rich. This experience is understood by few. For instance, you lay your head on the pillow and easily fall asleep. But do you understand the value of it?

If you look at your fate from the perspective of contentment, you realize your well-being and see how many people around you are experiencing difficulties. Those who criticize you cannot truly appreciate your joys. If you are content with your situation, you understand how some people are incapable of appreciating your happy life.

Given to you – be gracious

Taken away from you – be gracious

Given a family – be gracious

Without a family – be gracious

Because in them, there is both responsibility and opportunity. However, no matter how you solve one problem, a new one will always arise. Finding an answer to one question, you will encounter another.

It's like a game where you are constantly searching and repeating the solution. If a person

doesn't understand the truth of this world, they become disillusioned, gloomy, and sick. This is precisely why many people in America and Europe face psychological problems. Because a person doesn't understand what this world is, what they need. They are born, go to school, enter university, get money, a car, a house, a wife, indulge in vice – everything is there, but they don't understand why they have all this, what they are really seeking. That's why at this time, when Allah gives meaning to your world, it is crucial to believe in Qadar. Ultimately, when you improve your connection with Qadar, your relationships with Allah, with people, and with yourself also improve. Otherwise, it will be the opposite.

REFERENCES

1. Ahmad Damanhuriy "Fiqhul hadith"
2. Sheikh Muhammad Sodiq Muhammad Yusuf. The series of books 'Golden Chain' (Sahih Bukhari). - Tashkent.: Hilol Nashr, 2013. - 672 p.
3. Sheikh Muhammad Sodiq Muhammad Yusuf. The series of books 'Oltin Silsila' (Sahih Bukhari). - Tashkent.: Hilol Nashr, 2013. - 672 p.
4. "Kizlarjon" by Odinakhon Muhammad Sodik. - Tashkent.: Hilol Nashr, 2020. - 192 p.